

Advancing RDM Careers

A Framework for Expert Education in Finland

Final report¹

This report is a summary of the original, longer report by the [working group](#). The summary has been prepared by Jukka Rantasaari*, Susanna Nykyri**, Manna Satama***, and Anne-Marie Tuikka****.

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Abstract

The report details Finland's growing need for Research Data Management (RDM) experts and for formal education in this field. It describes a specialised training program that includes environmental scanning, stakeholder collaboration, and a modular curriculum that caters to a variety of sectors. The report concludes with the selection of Tampere University for program implementation and emphasises the importance of continuous stakeholder engagement and international collaboration, inspired by the University of Vienna's model.

Introduction

Finland faces a critical gap in professional training for Research Data Management (RDM) experts, who play a pivotal role in maintaining research data integrity. This report underscores the need for a formal education pathway that aligns with workplace needs and evolving demands in academia and other fields. The report summarises the work by the Professionalisation of RDM Experts Working Group with the aim of establishing a specialised training program to address this need.

At the moment, often self-taught RDM professionals are increasingly involved in training newcomers in their organisations. Furthermore, the existing training programs are inadequate in their coverage of essential RDM skills. The proposed systematic, high-quality education program seeks to remedy these gaps. The program aligns with Finnish legislative standards and responds to Europe's significant demand for data stewards and enhanced data management skills among young researchers.

¹ Roadmap for professional qualification of data management experts working group. (2024). Advancing RDM Careers: A Framework for Expert Education in Finland (1.0). Zenodo.

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How Did We Work

Formed under AVOTT, the national Open Science and Research Coordination, the working group of approximately 45 members initially conducted an environmental scan of data steward education, followed by brainstorming sessions on RDM qualifications and skills. A roadmap to professionalise data management training was outlined focusing on five key steps: raising awareness of educational needs, detailing the education's content, identifying an organiser, establishing a sustainable business model, and building trust in the training's value.

The working group was split into three subgroups with regular six-week updates taking place together. It convened 17 times from February 2022 to January 2024 to develop RDM training.

The subgroups worked on certain themes: one focused on justifying RDM education needs, one outlined educational content, and one focused on securing organisation and funding.

Work of the Subgroups

Subgroup 1: Building awareness of the need for education

Subgroup 1 was tasked with building awareness of RDM education through promotional materials, identifying key audiences including the Finnish Ministry of Education and Culture, higher education institutions, companies, and the AVOTT community. They developed a PowerPoint presentation as their main promotional tool, covering topics such as the background and aims of the project, the need for data steward professionalisation, the relationship between data stewards and other professionals working with data, the current situation internationally and nationally, and recommendations. This presentation has been utilised in various meetings and conferences, with the education organiser set to continue the material's development and dissemination.

Subgroup 2: Outlining the Main Content of the Training Needed

Subgroup 2 was responsible for developing a modular training curriculum for RDM experts, designed to enhance both technical and interpersonal skills. The subgroup's approach included aligning the curriculum with national and international standards, and incorporating existing resources while avoiding any unnecessary duplication with them. Skills4EOSC's harmonisation efforts surrounding data management professionalisation as well as drawing parallels with the University of Vienna's accredited certificate course heavily influenced the curriculum design.

Subgroup 2's comprehensive curriculum covered essential RDM areas and was designed to cater to different RDM professional profiles, considering policy-oriented, research-oriented, data science/analysis-oriented, and infrastructure-oriented roles, with an additional 'agent of change' role that can be adopted by all. The curriculum proposed five modules, each addressing critical aspects of RDM, with optional add-on training for specialised topics:

- Module 1: the basics of RDM and open science
- Module 2: IT and data science fundamentals
- Module 3: FAIR Data principles in the research data lifecycle
- Module 4: RDM support such as consulting and training

- Module 5: practical application through project work.

These modules could be tailored to suit various professional roles, enabling participants to apply knowledge within their own contexts, targeting professionals, researchers, and advanced students.

Subgroup 3: Find an Organiser and Start-Up Funding for the Education

Subgroup 3 focused on finding a coordinator and securing funding for RDM education. The chosen organiser needed to be credible, capable of awarding credits, and knowledgeable about RDM needs. The funding models considered did not rely on basic higher education funding, with a preference for a participant-pay approach to ensure sustainability.

Tampere University was selected for planning and organising, supported by a grant from the Ministry of Education and Culture. The grant will cover the costs for a coordinator, content creation, and administrative expenses. The training plan envisions a year of development, followed by a modular 15-credit program with on-site and online sessions, including a practical component.

The program design allows for full or partial completion, with the first iteration focused on equipping participants for various data management roles. Besides national partners such as CSC – IT Center for Science and the Open Science and Research Coordination (AVOTT) collaboration group, international collaboration is sought, particularly with the University of Vienna's data steward training, to enhance the program's quality and relevance.

Conclusions and Next Steps

The need for data management experts is widely acknowledged in the field, reflecting a common understanding among professionals. Based on discussions with various actors, the working group was convinced of the need for comprehensive education to support and enhance scientific research and data sharing. For this purpose, short courses or some tailoring of existing training would not be enough.

Consequently, the group decided to trust the insights of current research data management experts and external studies to shape the training program. It is crucial to raise awareness about the professional competence required in data management and the significance of targeted training.

The next steps for 2024 involve dedicated planning and preparation for the training, led by a hired coordinator. The inaugural training session will feature an on-site kickoff event, followed by online sessions, and culminate in a practical internship. Designed to be modular, the program allows for partial or full completion, with a certificate awarded for completing the full 15 credit program. The training is planned to be piloted twice, in 2025 and 2026, featuring a sustained partnership with CSC, AVOTT, and FSD (the Finnish Social Science Data Archive). Moreover, it aims to foster international collaboration to seek out joint training ventures. Finally, during the pilot stage, the continuum for the necessary RDM expert training will be designed.

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